

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 1, Выпуск 1, 30 сентября

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ORGANIZING ENGLISH LESSONS

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Annotation. This article discusses the importance of using new pedagogical technologies in the organization of English lessons. It is very important to teach a foreign language in higher and secondary education, because a foreign language plays an important role in the comprehensive development of students. One of the most pressing issues of our time is to educate the younger generation in the spirit of love and devotion to the motherland, national pride, high morals and spirituality, pride in our ancient and rich heritage, national and universal values through the teaching of foreign languages.

Key words: foreign language, pedagogue, innovation, technology, method, communication, dialogue, computer, "Debate" method, speech, philology. Introduction. It is becoming increasingly clear that the education system of our country is undergoing significant changes. It is no exaggeration to say that learning foreign languages has become a part of human life. This requires constant research of new technologies and methods in higher and secondary education, especially in the pedagogical activities of English teachers. In the traditional way, it has become a tradition for us to present our ideas to the students in a simple way through simple oral examples.[5] As knowledge of a foreign language is very important today, one of the most pressing issues in education is the reform of the system of foreign language teaching, the application of advanced teaching methods in the teaching process using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies. turned. The main reasons why educational institutions today pay special attention to the use of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process are:

- First of all, the Law "On Education" and the "National Training Program" pay special attention to the implementation of developmental education in the context of the possibility of personal development education in pedagogical technologies.

- Second, the systematic use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process allows for their widespread introduction;

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- Third, pedagogical technology encourages the teacher to pre-design the technological chain, from the objectives of the educational process to the establishment of a diagnostic system and control over the process;

- Fourth, their use because pedagogical technology is based on the use of new tools and information methods;

Linguistic skills include knowing the language system and the rules to be used in communicating in English. Particular attention is paid to the socio-political development of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan, the acquisition of terms and communication skills that reflect its market economy, foreign policy development with foreign countries.

The most important areas of pedagogical and career choice are the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a market economy, the expansion of international business relations, the development of new directions in the national economy. Linguistic and ethnographic skills include the knowledge of the features of a country's socio-cultural development, its history and status, and the development of speech based on them.

At present, the methodology of teaching foreign languages includes the goals and content of foreign language teaching, the laws, methods, means, ways, methods of studying and teaching the education system, as well as the use of foreign languages. is seen as a science that carries out the upbringing of birds.

It is based on a deeper knowledge of the written forms of students' speech, which requires them to express their ideas beautifully in English.

Literature review. Theoretical and methodological bases of development of teaching technologies, their introduction in educational process are reflected in scientific researches carried out by scientists of the Republic and foreign countries. In particular, S.S.Gulamov, A.A.Abdukadirov, M.Oripov, R.H.Hamdammov, N.Toylakov, E.S.Polat, R.England, A.S.Lauzen, S.Novas, W.Souder and a number of other scientists have dealt with this issue.[10]

Research Methodology. Today, we are working with students on the basis of various slides, video tutorials, interesting puzzles and many new ideas, using the techniques of the new era, without using the same old methods of work. not only arouses their interest in science, but also helps them to keep in mind the information they receive through the eyes and ears. By using a variety of English crossword puzzles, fun exercises, and a number of interactive methods in the classroom, learners can apply what they have learned in the future.

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Analysis and results. The next criterion for choosing interactive methods is their relevance to the nature of the content. The content of the method is also defined as part of the movement. It is therefore doubtful that this criterion should be taken into account. One method is to fully explain the content of the topic, while the other allows you to master it in a positive way.[4]

Another criterion for choosing interactive methods is that they are fully compatible with the learning opportunities of students, that is, to ensure the unity of internal and external conditions for effective learning activities. The use of interactive teaching methods should be tailored to the individual capabilities of the educator. The theory and practice of this educator's teaching methods take into account the degree to which the theories of cognition with the laws of the teaching process are armed with the theory of educational content and other existing laws.

The next criterion for choosing interactive methods is their compatibility with the forms of organization of the learning process. By the way, general, group and individual forms of teaching require different methods. For example, if the Debate method is a discussion between two students, the Brainstorming method requires the participation of all students in the group. The plan is to show the students pre-prepared video materials (slides, short videos, cartoons) using a video projector or electronic whiteboard, while at the same time increasing their attention to this lesson. we will have the opportunity to have a fun lesson.[9] Then we can use a variety of motivational methods to ensure that students remember the lesson until the next lesson, and a number of other interactive methods to achieve high results.

At a time when in our country today the focus is on the education system, in the process of teaching English and the organization of lessons, teachers learn modern innovative technologies, ideas, different methods of different directions, already. the use of interactive methods, which have become a topical task today, rather than known methods, serves to form new thinking and knowledge skills of the younger generation.[3]

Modern interactive methods in foreign language teaching methods have been developed by scientists and have proven to be more effective than traditional methods. Interactive methods significantly increase the knowledge potential of the learning process compared to traditional methods. Because in interactive methods, the student thinks independently and works in partnership with the teacher. When teaching a foreign language using modern technologies, the student plans the lesson process, engages in it on the basis of the curriculum, chooses teaching methods

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jointly by the student and the teacher, participate in the discussion of the study material. Students help each other.[1]

One of the current issues is to educate the younger generation in the spirit of love and devotion to the motherland, national pride, high morals and spirituality, pride in our ancient and rich heritage, national and universal values through the teaching of foreign languages. Radical reforms in the global education system raise the problem of creating the necessary conditions for students to learn foreign languages perfectly, to express themselves in all areas with knowledge of a foreign language, to develop their oral and written speech in a foreign language.

In the reform of the education system of the Republic, the coordination of curricula in accordance with international standards, based on foreign experience, became the basis for improving the system of higher pedagogical education. In the context of Uzbekistan, the radical reform of the quality of education on the basis of foreign experience, taking into account our national mentality and traditions, is a requirement of the times.[8]

Therefore, in order to form the ability to read the original literature on the specialty, to participate in oral communication in a foreign language in the process of production of future personnel and finding the necessary information for scientific purposes in the higher education system of the republic classes are being held.

Every citizen of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan must be able to read the original literature in a foreign language, understand the text and use it in their profession. In addition, he should be able to communicate freely in a foreign language with his interlocutor on a given topic. After all, learning foreign languages is a requirement of today's globalized world.[2]

In our country, thanks to independence, special attention is paid to the teaching of foreign languages. Thousands of foreign language teachers have been trained, all conditions have been created for the staff to improve their skills in our country and abroad, multimedia textbooks in English, German and French, electronic resources for learning English have been prepared. The organization of language rooms is a clear proof of this. The main goal is to create conditions for young people to use the achievements of world civilization and information resources around the world, to develop international cooperation and dialogue, based on the education of the younger generation in foreign languages and the training of specialists who are fluent in those languages.[7]

Conclusion. Upon graduation, students are required to be able to receive, comprehend, and express their ideas orally and in writing, both orally and in writing.

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In higher education institutions that do not specialize in languages, the number of teaching hours is given in the curricula of those institutions. In non-philological educational institutions, foreign languages are taught on the basis of special curricula. Since such programs and textbooks have not yet been developed for our English special non-philological educational institutions, teachers in such Uzbek-language educational institutions use a variety of textbooks and manuals, taking into account the specifics of the direction.

Another way to meet modern requirements is to reduce the amount of redundant material for students and simplify the learning process. These are taken into account in the new foreign language program. The teacher approaches this in terms of students' comprehensive practical mastery of the material.

In short, it is very important to teach a foreign language in higher education institutions that do not specialize in languages, because the foreign language plays an important role in preparing students for full development. Today's information society can be described as a knowledge-based society. For example, the main activity of countries, companies and individuals is education.[6] In addition to the technologies of acquisition, processing and storage of knowledge, the technologies of teaching and transmission of knowledge are of great importance.

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